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FORMING INTENDING TEACHERS' HEALTH PRESERVING COMPETENCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Professional training in higher educational institutions is determined not only by the amount of obtained knowledge, but also by solving the problem of preserving and strengthening health, students' need for healthy lifestyle, the need to find and implement ways to form their health preserving competence. The article deals with the problem of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of HEI. The current state of research of the specified problem was analyzed in the paper, the maintenance of the concept "health preserving competence of intending teacher", the structure of the investigated phenomenon, including value-motivational, cognitive, operational-activity and reflexive components was specified. Criteria, indicators and levels of formation of the studied competence were determined. The pedagogical conditions of its forming were revealed and theoretically substantiated: creating and realizing integral educational and methodical support by supplementing the content of disciplines of the professional and practical training cycle and practice with the health preserving component; forming the need for self-education, developing the ability to self-control and professional self-assessment of health preserving competence; creating the healthy educational environment. The model of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the process of professional training, suggested in the educational environment of HEI, includes three blocks: target (coverage of the purpose, tasks, principles and approaches), organizational and semantic (pedagogical conditions, pedagogical technologies, concretized by organizational forms, methods and the maintenance of training) and reflective and effective (criteria, indicators and levels of health competence). The results of the experimental verification of the pedagogical conditions of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers were given

Keywords: Health preserving competence, intending teacher, professional training, pedagogical conditions, the model of forming, health care, health preserving activity

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1. Introduction

In the process of modernizing the education system of Ukraine in the framework of its integration into the European educational space, the problem of preserving and strengthening the health of the young generation becomes especially relevant. Its solving is closely connected with the reset of approaches to forming intending teachers' universal values of maintaining and strengthening health, healthy lifestyle; readiness to search for new mechanisms and forms of health care for students and introducing health preserving technologies in the educational process.

The importance of the problem of students' health preserving can be proved by attention to it of the world organizations. In 2003 the World Health Organization issued the report for governments, policy-makers, non-government organizations, community leaders and educators with the profound analysis of the theories and principles of developing students'

health skills; suggesting priority actions for preserving students' health; planning and evaluating such kind of school education [1]. Considerable attention to the importance of future world citizens' health skills was drawn in the UNESCO report of 2016. The authors stress the leading role of health for the well-being of people and sustainable development of societies and the inter-relations between education and health. The strategies for the development of students' health skills were suggested in the report [2].

The normative base of the professional pedagogical training in Ukraine is defined by the Law of Ukraine "On Education" [3], the National Doctrine of Education Development in Ukraine (2002), the Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education" (2014), the National Strategy for Education Development in Ukraine till 2021, the Concept of development of pedagogical education [4], the Concept of development of education of Ukraine for the period 2015–2025 (2015) and other regulations, govern-

ing the activities of higher education institutions. In addition, the need to strengthen the requirements in the field of health preserving and responsibility for their own health is emphasized in the Concept of the State National Social Programme “Youth of Ukraine for 2016–2020” (2015), the Concept of positive motivation for children’s and youth’s healthy lifestyle (2004), the draft law “On approval of the National Programme ‘Health 2020: the Ukrainian dimension’” [5], the Concept of forming new health care system (2014), the National strategy for physical activity in Ukraine till 2025 “Physical activity – healthy lifestyle – healthy nation” [6] and others.

2. Literary review

Different aspects of the issue of training educators for professional activity in general and for forming their health preserving competence (HPC) as one of its aspects in the conditions of modern education are investigated in the considerable number of scientific researches, represented in the publications of the Ukrainian and foreign scientists. Different pedagogical conditions of developing future teachers’ healthcare competency like enhancing motivation, creating learning space, designing the proper content etc. were thoroughly researched theoretically and practically confirmed in the result of the pedagogical experiment [7]. The problem of students’ limited health literacy was touched upon in the research, conducted in three American universities where the educational programs for health education professionals were analyzed and the gaps and weaknesses in their training were identified with suggestions for practical applying the results of the investigation [8]. The importance of health education in training teachers was researched by the Australian scientist and it was concluded, that such education is obligatory as it is helpful both for intending teachers and their future students. The research included students’ well-being, social and emotional learning and the impact of health education on the quality of life of students [9]. The European scientists from different countries applied Delphi method for their researching teachers’ competencies in health education. The analysis of the data, gathered from the European states, Australia and Canada, led to the conclusion that the core competencies include students’ knowledge, skills and attitudes, while there are differences in health education between the countries and within them [10].

However, despite the significant achievements, it should be noted, that in higher education institutions (HEIs) in Ukraine insufficient attention is paid to forming health preserving competence of intending educators [11]. The pedagogical technologies and health preserving models, developed by scientists, allow to single out a number of aspects of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers [12].

This, in turn, requires the improvement of the technology of organizing the educational process in higher education institutions in accordance with the changes of priorities in the current conditions [13].

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The article is aimed at presenting sound and experimentally tested pedagogical conditions for forming

health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of HEI.

To achieve the goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To find out the problem of protection and promotion of youth health, taking into account the current epidemiological situation.

2. To establish that professional training in higher educational institutions is determined not only by the amount of obtained knowledge, but also by solving the problem of preserving and strengthening health.

3. To analyze the concept of health preserving competence of intending teachers.

4. To determine the structure of health competence of future teachers.

5. To determine the pedagogical conditions for the formation of health preserving competence of future teachers in the educational environment of HEI.

6. To define the criteria for the formation of health competence.

7. To describe the model of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of HEI.

8. To experimentally confirm the effectiveness of pedagogical conditions for the formation of health-preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of HEI.

4. Materials and Methods

To achieve the outlined aim and fulfill certain tasks during the research, a set of methods was used, namely: theoretical – analysis of the philosophical, psychological and pedagogical, educational and methodical literature, normative and legal documents, regulating the activity of education and healthcare, for finding out the state of development of the problem. Modelling to develop a model for forming health preserving competence of intending teachers. System analysis to substantiate the pedagogical conditions for forming this competence. Empirical – observation of the educational process, interviews, polls, testing, surveys, methods of expert assessment, self-assessment, analysis of the results of educational activities to diagnose the level of health preserving competence. Pedagogical experiment (stating, formative, control stages) in order to study the state of formation of health preserving competence of intending teachers and check the effectiveness of the pedagogical conditions of its forming in the educational environment of HEI. Statistical – at the stating and control stages of the experiment, the CG and EG were compared according to Pearson agreement criterion, mathematical processing of results, quantitative analysis, display in tabular and graphical forms in order to capture and summarize the results of the experimental research, determine their statistical significance and ensure reliability and objectivity.

The research and experimental work was organized and conducted on the basis of Oleksandr Dovzhenko Hlukhiv National Pedagogical University, Taras Shevchenko Chernihiv National Pedagogical University, Ukrainian Engineering and Pedagogical Academy, M. P. Drahomanov National Pedagogical University. The study involved three stages of scientific and pedagogical research: stating, forming and control. The experimental work covered 368 students, of which 186 people formed

control (CG) and experimental (EG) – 182, as well as 14 teachers of these educational institutions.

The stating stage was aimed at developing the program and research methodology; determining indicators, criteria and levels of formation of health preserving competence; developing methods for measuring and processing the results of the experiment; selecting control and experimental groups; conducting the stating tests.

The forming stage was aimed at experimental verifying reasonable pedagogical conditions, introducing the model of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers.

The control stage involved the analyzing and systematizing the obtained data, clarifying the main provisions and formulating conclusions based on the results of the experimental work.

5. Result and Discussion

On the basis of generalization of the scientific achievements of the Ukrainian researchers the concept of “health competence of intending teacher” means a set of knowledge, skills and abilities, ways of thinking, qualities and values of a person that determines his/her ability to form and maintain their own physical, mental, social, spiritual health, and their future students’ ones in the further professional activities [14, 15]. The professional activity of each teacher integrates a number of functions, among which we single out the designing and organizational as those, directly related to health preserving activities. Qualitative implementation of the health preserving activities requires the formation of a high level of health preserving competence that is multicomponent in its structure [16]. In the course of the scientific research, the structure of health preserving competence of intending teachers was determined as a combination of values and motivational, cognitive, operational and activity and reflective components.

The content of the value-motivational component provides the understanding of the importance and place of health preserving technologies in the future pedagogical activities, the need to acquire knowledge about health technologies, focus on restoring and maintaining the health of students.

The cognitive component is related to the system of knowledge about the laws of healthy lifestyle, modern health technologies, tools, forms and methods of health work with students and pupils.

The operational and activity component presupposes that intending teachers possess the ability to keep to healthy lifestyle and form motivation for healthy lifestyle in their students, to plan and implement in the educational process preventive measures and health preserving technologies.

The reflective component is focused on optimizing the health preserving activities of intending teachers through the ability to self-analysis of healthy lifestyle, self-reflection, self-control and adjusting these activities.

The analysis of the content of professional training of teachers and the educational environment of universities in terms of our study revealed a number of significant problems, including the lack of system in forming health preserving competence.

Having taken into account the peculiarities of the professional activity of teachers and summarized the scientific developments and pedagogical experience of the HEIs, applied the method of expert evaluation, the authors determined the pedagogical conditions for forming health preserving competence of teachers in the educational environment of HEIs.

First, there is a need to create and implement a holistic educational and methodological support by supplementing the content of the disciplines of the cycle of professional and practical training and practice with the health preserving component. The educational process should be designed the way for intending teachers to master the basics of health and health preserving, as well as the organizational principles of the educational process with the use of health-preserving educational technologies.

The second pedagogical condition is forming intending teachers' needs for self-education, developing the ability to self-control and professional self-assessment of health preserving competence. It requires an organic combination in the educational process of individual and independent tasks of health preserving content, active creative work of students with the use of self-acquired knowledge, their mastery of practical skills in coping with the professional situations, aimed at implementing health preserving technologies and self-assessment.

Studying the process of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of higher educational institutions, the authors came to the conclusion about the need for its modernization, in particular its components – ecological (hygienic, aromatic, environmental components), emotional and behavioral (communicative culture, psychological climate, style and behavior), verbal (speech culture, clarity of wording, reduction of authoritarian tone in communication, absence of word-parasites and obscene language), culturological (art therapy, bibliotherapy, music therapy, drawing therapy). It should be noted, that the creation of an educational and health-friendly environment presupposes the availability of appropriate infrastructure in the higher educational institutions, providing proper sanitary and hygienic conditions for dwelling, catering, educating and training students, as well as conditions for their active learning, recreation and harmonious development. Coordinated activity of all services and divisions of higher educational institutions is necessary for the realization of this condition.

Based on the conceptual ideas of the study, the structural and functional model of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers was developed, taking into account the peculiarities of the educational environment of universities (Fig. 1). It contains the following blocks: aims, organization and content, and reflection and results.

The aims block provides coverage of the goal of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of the higher educational institutions. According to the aims, the main tasks of this process were formulated: creating motivation, systematizing the acquired knowledge, forming abilities and skills, ability to reflection.

For effective forming health preserving competence the expediency of applying competence, axiological, differentiated, research, system, technological, personality-oriented approaches, as well as general didactic and specific principles (professional responsibility, observing clear ethical rules, confidentiality of obtained data on health state and way of life, feedback), was grounded [17].

The organization and content block covers pedagogical conditions, pedagogical technologies, which are specified through organization forms, methods and content of training of intending teachers in the process of their professional training. Realizing the aims and tasks of forming health preserving competence of intending

teachers in the suggested model was provided by organizational forms (lectures, practical and laboratory classes, conferences, research, individual and independent work) and methods (problem teaching the educational material, discussion, competitions, business game, round table, project method, modeling, solving pedagogical problems) of training [18]. It was assumed, that classes and independent work of students are conducted using pedagogical technologies of contextual, interactive, problem-based learning, project, training and information technology [19]. The content of work, aimed at forming health preserving competence of intending teachers, covers the disciplines of the cycle of professional and practical training and independent work of students [20] (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Structural and functional model of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of higher educational institutions

The reflection and results block provides evaluating, analyzing and correcting the results of the formation of health preserving competence of intending teachers. It reflects the criteria (values and motivation, cognitive, operation and activity, reflective), their indicators, levels of formation (low, medium, high) of the studied competence.

The introduction of the proposed model in the educational process of higher educational institutions requires a certain method of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers. The analysis of curricula and programs made it possible to identify disciplines of the cycle of professional and practical training with the potential to form this competence: “Fundamentals of labor protection” and methods of disciplines (depending on specialization). In the context of the research tasks, their content was purposefully supplemented and expanded: the content module “Fundamentals of health and health preserving” was introduced into the program of the discipline “Fundamentals of professional safety”, which provides the following topics of lectures: “Theoretical aspects of health and health preserving”, “Social maladaptation and human health”, “Methodological and pedagogical problems of health in professional education”, “Health preserving pedagogical technologies in the system of professional education”. In order to improve skills, abilities and gain experience in the field of health preserving, the following topics of practical classes were provided: “Forming psychophysical basics of health” and “Health preserving activity in the educational process”. The module offers students to work independently in the form of developing the health program (treatment and prevention complex, which will allow in a short time to eliminate the effects of stress, increase efficiency, reduce the risk of professional diseases).

Introducing the content module “Organizing the educational process with the use of health preserving learning technologies” in the program of methodological disciplines involves students’ mastering the methodological principles of health preserving competence. In particular, it was planned to learn the following topics: “Analysis of basic concepts of health preserving competence of teachers”, “Methodological aspects of organizing the educational process with students using health preserving technologies of teaching”, “Modern approaches to the implementation of health preserving technologies in schools”, “Interactive methods of implementing health preserving technologies in the educational process”. The individual work of students involves the implementation of creative tasks (development of advertising on healthy life style; scenario of preventive and health activities with students and materials for its implementation; presentation of the valeological direction; health and preventive lectures on health as a unity of physical, mental, spiritual and social components and systematic approach to forming human health) and writing a scientific paper. Performing such work will bring students closer to the conditions that are as focused as possible on their future professional activities for the implementation of health preserving technologies.

In order to work out the acquired skills and abilities of students a number of cases with health-oriented tasks in real professional activity were developed: to determine the general state of physical and psychological health of students; to design educational activities, aimed at health preserving, etc.

The stating stage was aimed at developing the program and research methodology; determining indicators, criteria and levels of formation of health preserving competence; developing methods for measuring and processing the results of the experiment; selecting control and experimental groups; conducting the stating tests.

In order to diagnose the level of health preserving competence of intending teachers, the following criteria were defined: values and motivation (indicators: understanding the importance and place of health preserving technologies in the future professional activities, the need to master knowledge on health preserving technologies, focus on restoring and maintaining the health of students); cognitive (indicators: knowledge of the laws of healthy lifestyle; modern health technologies; means, forms and methods of health work with students); operational (indicators: the ability to adhere to healthy lifestyle and form motivation for healthy lifestyle in students, to plan and implement in educational work with students preventive and health measures, health preserving technologies); reflective (indicators: the ability to self-analysis of healthy lifestyle, self-reflection, self-control and adjustment of health activities).

According to these criteria and indicators, the following levels of health competence of intending teachers in the process of their professional training were defined:

– high (characterized by a high level of indicators of each component of health preserving competence: a stable understanding of the importance and place of health preserving technologies in the future professional activities; a conscious need to master knowledge of health preserving technologies; focus on restoring and maintaining the health of students, a dynamic system of knowledge about the laws of healthy lifestyle, modern health preserving technologies, tools, forms and methods of health preserving, a high level of skills of healthy lifestyle and forming motivation for healthy lifestyle in students, planning and implementing in educational work with students preventive and health measures and health technologies; the ability to self-analysis, self-reflection, self-control and adjustment of health activities), formed at the high level;

– medium (involves partial manifestation of indicators of each component of health preserving technologies: an unconvincing understanding of the importance and place of health preserving technologies in the future professional activities; situational manifestation of the need to acquire knowledge on health preserving technologies; periodic focus on restoring and maintaining the health of students; sufficient knowledge of healthy lifestyle, modern health preserving technologies, means, forms and methods of health work, a sufficient level of skills to comply with healthy lifestyle and the formation of motivation for healthy lifestyle in students, planning and implementation in educational work with students of preventive and health preserv-

ing measures and health technologies, partial ability to self-analysis, self-reflection, self-control and adjustment of health preserving activity);

– low (mainly due to the initial degree of manifestation of the components of the health preserving technologies: lack of awareness of the importance and place of health preserving technologies in the future professional activities; an unformed need to master knowledge of health preserving technologies; insufficient focus on restoring and maintaining the health of students; fragmentary knowledge, means, forms and methods of health-preserving work, an insufficient level of formation of skills of observing healthy lifestyle and forming motivation to healthy lifestyle in students, planning and implementation in educational work with students of preventive and health measures and health preserving technologies, undeveloped ability to self-analysis, self-reflection, self-control and adjustment of health preserving activity).

According to the results of the stating stage of the experiment, it was found, that health preserving competence of students was mainly formed at low and average levels (especially according to cognitive and operational criteria). They lack clear understanding of the importance and place of health preserving technologies in the future professional activities; the need for mastering knowledge on this problem was not fully manifested; lack of knowledge about the means, forms and methods of organizing health preserving work with students was recorded; the ability to plan preventive and health improv-

ing measures in the educational work with students was not formed and there was no ability to self-analysis, self-reflection, self-control and adjustment of health preserving activity.

The forming stage was aimed at experimental verifying reasonable pedagogical conditions, introducing the model of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers.

At this stage, the educational process with the students of the experimental group was organized in accordance with the defined pedagogical conditions for forming health preserving competence of intending teachers. The implementation was carried out in the process of face to face (lectures, practical) classes and in research, individual and independent work.

In the control groups of each educational institution, the educational process of professional training of teachers was carried out traditionally.

The control stage involved the analyzing and systematizing the obtained data, clarifying the main provisions and formulating conclusions based on the results of the experimental work. The dynamics of the formation of health preserving competence of intending teachers in the process of their professional training (Table 1) shows a significant change in high and low levels. The medium level showed insignificant dynamics and remained at almost the same level due to the simultaneous transition of some students from low level of health preserving competence to medium, and from medium to high.

Table 1

Dynamics of the formed level of health preserving competence of intending teachers in the process of professional training (%)

Components	Levels	Experimental group (182 persons)		Control group (186 persons)		χ^2	
		Before	After	Before	After	Before	After
Values and motivation	Low	33.5	9.9	35.5	22.0	0.53	19.42
	Medium	23.6	26.4	25.3	30.2		
	High	42.9	63.7	39.2	47.8		
Cognitive	Low	52.2	22.5	47.8	29.6	0.79	7.07
	Medium	24.7	37.4	26.4	43.0		
	High	23.1	40.1	25.8	27.4		
Operation and activity	Low	49.4	24.7	47.8	34.9	0.65	6.53
	Medium	35.2	45.1	38.8	43.1		
	High	15.4	30.2	13.4	22.0		
Reflective	Low	18.6	14.8	21.0	16.6	0.77	6.02
	Medium	44.0	32.5	39.8	42.5		
	High	37.4	52.7	39.2	40.9		

The analysis of the results of the experiment showed an increase in the share of students with the high level of health preserving competence due to the introduction of certain pedagogical conditions for forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of higher educational institutions. In terms of the levels of formation of health preserving competence, the following results were obtained: at the beginning 42.9 % of students with the high level of formation of the values and motivational component were recorded, while at the end the result was 63.7 %. According to the cogni-

tive component, the researchers also state an increase in the number of students with the high level of competence formation: from 23.1 % at the beginning of the experiment to 40.1 % at the end. The percentage of students with the high level of competence in the operational component increased from 15.4 % to 30.2 %. The positive dynamics was traced in the formation of health preserving competence by the reflective component: from 37.4 % to 52.7 % of students. In the control group, the shifts were expressed to a considerably lower extent.

At the stating and control stages of the experiment, the CG and EG were compared according to Pearson agreement criterion. At the initial stage of the experiment, no significant differences in certain criteria between the groups were found (critical value $\chi^2=5.99$). After the implementation of the experimental program, a significant difference between the control and experimental groups was recorded.

Thus, the pedagogical experiment confirmed the correctness of our assumptions that the identified and theoretically substantiated pedagogical conditions increase the effectiveness of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of higher educational institutions. The differences between the results of the study, conducted with students of the control and experimental groups, are reliable according to all the main criteria. The indicators of the experimental group significantly exceeded the indicators of the control group.

The study does not cover all the aspects of solving the problem of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of higher educational institutions. We consider determining the methods of forming health preserving competence of teachers, taking into account the specifics of their future specialization, to be the promising areas of further researches.

6. Conclusion

1. It was found, that the problem of protection and promotion of youth health, taking into account the current epidemiological situation, is one of the most pressing not only in our society, but also in the world as a whole.

2. It was found, that professional training in higher educational institutions is determined not only by the amount of obtained knowledge, but also by solving the problem of preserving and strengthening health, students need for healthy lifestyle, the need to find and implement ways to form their health preserving competence.

3. The content of the concept of “health preserving competence of the intending teacher” reflects person’s set of knowledge, skills and abilities, ways of thinking, qualities and values, which determines his/her ability to form and maintain their own physical, mental, social, spiritual health, while studying at the university and for the further professional activity.

4. The structure of health preserving competence contains a number of components, the degree of formation of which indicates the ability of intending teachers to health preserving activity. The component composition of health preserving competence is focused on the systematizing and specifying the needs that form the motive of activity (values and motivational); mastering the system of knowledge (cognitive); mastering skills (operational and activity); self-analysis and development of professionally significant abilities (reflective).

5. Pedagogical conditions for forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educa-

tional environment of HEI are the following: creating and implementing the holistic educational and methodological support by supplementing the content of disciplines of the cycle of professional and practical training with the health preserving component; forming the need for self-education, developing the ability to self-control and professional self-assessment of health preserving competence; creating the healthy educational environment that contains ecological, emotional and behavioral, verbal, cultural components.

6. Criteria for the formation of health preserving competence are: values and motivational (understanding the importance and place of health preserving technologies in the future professional activity of a teacher, the need to master knowledge about health preserving technologies, focus on restoring and preserving the health of students); cognitive (knowledge of the laws of healthy lifestyle; modern health technologies; means, forms and methods of health preserving work with students); operational (ability to adhere to healthy lifestyle and form motivation for healthy lifestyle in students, plan and implement in the educational work with students preventive measures and health preserving technologies) and reflective (ability to self-analysis of healthy lifestyle, self-reflection, self-control and adjustment of health preserving activity), which determine low, average, or high levels of its formation.

7. The structural and functional model of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of HEI includes three blocks: target (coverage of the purpose, tasks, principles and approaches), organizational and semantic (pedagogical conditions, pedagogical technologies, concretized by organizational forms, methods and the maintenance of training) and reflective and effective (criteria, indicators and levels of health competence). The theoretical and methodological basis of the model is grounded on competence, axiological, differentiated, research, system, technological, personality-oriented methodological approaches.

8. The effectiveness of the identified and theoretically substantiated pedagogical conditions, the effectiveness of the developed method of forming health preserving competence of intending teachers in the educational environment of HEI was experimentally confirmed.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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References

1. Skills for health. Skills-based health education including life skills: An important component of a Child-Friendly/Health-Promoting School (2003). The World Health Organization, 83. Available at: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42818>

2. UNESCO strategy on education for health and well-being: contributing to the sustainable development goals (2016). United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000246453>
3. Pro osvitu (2017). Zakon Ukrainy No. 2145-VIII. 05.09.2017. Vidomosti Verkhovnoi Rady, 38-39, 380. Available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/card/2145-19>
4. Kontsepsiia rozvytku pedahohichnoi osvity (2018). Ministerstvo osvity i nauky Ukrainy No. 776. 16.07.2018. Available at: <https://mon.gov.ua/ua/npa/pro-zatverdzhennya-koncepciyi-rozvytku-pedagogichnoyi-osviti>
5. Kontsepsiia derzhavnoi prohramy «Zdorov'ia 2020: ukrainskyi vymir» (2011). Kabinet ministriv Ukrainy No. 1164-r. 31.10.2011. Available at: <https://www.kmu.gov.ua/npas/244717787>
6. Pro Natsionalnu stratehiu zdorovoho rukhu v Ukraini na period do 2025 roku «Rukhova diialnist – zdorovi sposib zhyttia – zdorova natsiia» (2016). Rozporiadzhennia Prezydenta Ukrainy No. 42/2016. 09.02.2016. Available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/42/2016?lang=uk#Text>
7. Maksymchuk, B., Matviichuk, T., Solovyov, V., Davydenko, H., Soichuk, R., Khurtenko, O. et. al. (2020). Developing Healthcare Competency in Future Teachers. Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala, 12 (3), 24–43. doi: <http://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/12.3/307>
8. Dawkins-Moultin, L., McKyer, L., McDonald, A. (2018). Health Literacy Competence of Health Education Students in Three Universities. Pedagogy in Health Promotion, 5 (2), 99–106. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1177/2373379918792936>
9. Yager, Z. (2011). Health Education in Teacher Education: Evaluation of Learning Design with Embedded Personal Wellness Learning and Assessment Focus. Australian Journal of Teacher Education, 36 (10). doi: <http://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2011v36n10.6>
10. Moynihan, S., Paakkari, L., Välimaa, R., Jourdan, D., Mannix-McNamara, P. (2015). Teacher Competencies in Health Education: Results of a Delphi Study. PLOS ONE, 10 (12), e0143703. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0143703>
11. Kesytska, I. L. (2018). Formuvannia tsinnosti zdorovoho sposobu zhyttia studentiv u protsesi fizychnoho vykhovannia. Kyiv, 278.
12. Danylenko, H. M., Ponomarova, L. I., Mezhybetska, I. V., Klyhina, I. A., Kuraksa, O. Yu. (2011). Formuvannia zdorov'iazberihaiuchoi povedinky sered uchniv profesiino-tekhnichnykh navchalnykh zakladiv. Osvita i zdorov'ia. Yevpatoriia, 234.
13. Yezhova, O. O. (2011). Health saving technology in educational system of formation of values related to health among students of vocational educational establishments. Pedahohichni nauky: teoriia, istoriia, innovatsiini tekhnologii, 3 (13), 65–74.
14. Samus, T. V. (2015). Formuvannia zdorov'iazberezhualnoi kompetentnosti maibutnykh inzheneriv-pedahohiv. Hlukhiv, 62.
15. Sohokon, O. (2019). Formation of health-saving competence of students of modern educational establishment. Pedahohichna osvita: teoriia i praktyka, 27 (2), 115–120.
16. Rudenko, L. A. (2019). Aktualizatsiia zdorov'iazberezhualnoho aspektu osvitnoho protsesu. Naukovyi visnyk Lotnoi akademii. Seriya: Pedahohichni nauky, 5, 218–223.
17. Samus, T. V. (2019). The healthcare of youth as a prerequisite of achieving the sustainable development of Ukraine. Naukovyi zhurnal. Innovatsiina pedahohika, 3 (10), 63–67.
18. Kovalchuk, V. I., Ihnatenko, S. V., Rosnovskiy, M. H., Ihnatenko, H. V., Vovk, B. I., Opanasenko, V. P. et. al.; Kovalchuk, V. I. (Ed.) (2020). Pidhotovka maibutnykh pedahohiv profesiinoho navchannia na zasadakh kompetentnisnoho pidkrodu. Hlukhiv, 221.
19. Ihnatenko, H. V., Opanasenko, V. P., Samus, T. V. (2017). Formuvannia metodychnoi kompetentnosti pedahohiv profesiinoho navchannia v protsesi pedahohichnykh praktyk. Sumy, 112.
20. Kovalchuk, V. I.; Kyrychenko, M. O., Serheieva, L. M. (Eds.) (2018). Profesiinyi rozvytok pedahohichnykh pratsivnykiv v umovakh informatsiinoho suspilstva. Vidkryta osvita: innovatsiini tekhnologii ta menedzhment. Kyiv, 133–157.

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